

Thermomechanics of a Kevlar cord suspension for cryogenic spacecraft instruments

Supplementary material and footnotes – René Wanders

Section 2. Mechanical model

- All tests presented here were performed on a single stage suspension to simplify the comparison between analysis and measurements of the dynamic behavior.
- The measurements to find the stiffness of the used 3 strand and 7 strand Kevlar were performed rapidly to minimize the effect of creep.
- Derivation of the stiffness matrix:

Cord 5 is aligned with the z-direction, it is under a pretension force F_0 and fixed at the top. If the bottom end is displaced with $\vec{s} = [0 \ 0 \ s_z \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$, then the force on the mass will be:

$$F_{z-z} = F_0 - ks_z$$

It is assumed that the cord is always in tension. The force acts in the z-direction, in any of the perpendicular directions it is zero. If the cord end is instead displaced in a perpendicular direction p (could be x or y) with displacement s_p , then the perpendicular force on the mass will be:

$$F_{p-p} = - \left(F_0 + k \left(\sqrt{L^2 + s_p^2} - L \right) \right) \frac{s_p}{\sqrt{L^2 + s_p^2}}$$

In this case the pretension contributes to the restoring force. For a small s_p this simplifies to:

$$F_{p-p} = - \frac{F_0}{L} s_p$$

The z-axis component of the force will be:

$$F_{z-p} = \left(F_0 + k \left(\sqrt{L^2 + s_p^2} - L \right) \right) \frac{L}{\sqrt{L^2 + s_p^2}}$$

This is not a restoring force, for a small displacement this simplifies to: $F_{z-p} = F_0$.

The linearized stiffness matrix for the single cord is:

$$\mathbf{K}_5 = \begin{bmatrix} k_{x-x} & k_{x-y} & k_{x-z} \\ k_{y-x} & k_{y-y} & k_{y-z} \\ k_{z-x} & k_{z-y} & k_{z-z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{F_0}{L} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{F_0}{L} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & k \end{bmatrix}$$

For the complete suspension the stiffness can be derived in the same way. If a small x-axis displacement $\vec{s} = [s_x \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$ is applied to the suspended mass, the force in each cord can be calculated. The location and orientations of each Kevlar cord can be retrieved from figure 2. The cord ends are located at:

$$\vec{a}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}(L + L_0) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ \frac{3}{4}(L + L_0) + \frac{R}{2} \\ -\frac{L + L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \vec{a}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ \frac{R}{2} \\ L + L_0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \vec{a}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}(L + L_0) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ -\frac{3}{4}(L + L_0) + \frac{R}{2} \\ -\frac{L + L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\vec{a}_4 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ -R \\ -\frac{L + L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \vec{a}_5 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -R \\ L + L_0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \vec{a}_6 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ -R \\ -\frac{L + L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\vec{a}_7 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}(L+L_0) + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ -\frac{3}{4}(L+L_0) + \frac{R}{2} \\ -\frac{L+L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}, & \vec{a}_8 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ \frac{R}{2} \\ L+L_0 \end{bmatrix}, & \vec{a}_9 &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}(L+L_0) + \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ \frac{3}{4}(L+L_0) + \frac{R}{2} \\ -\frac{L+L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix} \\
\vec{b}_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\left(\frac{L_0}{2} - R\right) \\ \frac{3}{4}L_0 + \frac{R}{2} \\ -\frac{L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}, & \vec{b}_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ \frac{R}{2} \\ L_0 \end{bmatrix}, & \vec{b}_3 &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\left(\frac{L_0}{2} - R\right) \\ -\frac{3}{4}L_0 + \frac{R}{2} \\ -\frac{L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix} \\
\vec{b}_4 &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}L_0 \\ -R \\ -\frac{L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}, & \vec{b}_5 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -R \\ L_0 \end{bmatrix}, & \vec{b}_6 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}L_0 \\ -R \\ -\frac{L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix} \\
\vec{b}_7 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\left(\frac{L_0}{2} + R\right) \\ \frac{3}{4}L_0 + \frac{R}{2} \\ -\frac{L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}, & \vec{b}_8 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \\ \frac{R}{2} \\ L_0 \end{bmatrix}, & \vec{b}_9 &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\left(\frac{L_0}{2} - R\right) \\ \frac{3}{4}L_0 + \frac{R}{2} \\ -\frac{L_0}{2} \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

The vector of cord 1 after displacing the mass with \vec{s} is \vec{v}_1 , the new cord length is $L_{new} = \|\vec{v}_1\|$. The magnitude of the force in the cord is:

$$\|\vec{F}_{1,x}\| = F_0 + k(L_{new} - L)$$

This force acts on the mass along vector \vec{v}_1 . It contains an x, y, and a z-component:

$$\vec{F}_{1,x} = \begin{bmatrix} F_{1,x-x} \\ F_{1,y-x} \\ F_{1,z-x} \end{bmatrix}$$

The x-component of the resultant force on the mass is the summation:

$$F_{x-x} = \sum_{n=1}^9 \vec{F}_{n,x-x}$$

The displacement in the x-direction might also cause a force on the mass in other directions:

$$F_{y-x} = \sum_{n=1}^9 \vec{F}_{n,y-x}, \dots$$

The linearized elements of the stiffness matrix are:

$$\begin{aligned}
k_{x-x} &= -\left. \frac{\partial F_{x-x}}{\partial s_x} \right|_{s_x=0}, \\
k_{y-x} &= -\left. \frac{\partial F_{y-x}}{\partial s_x} \right|_{s_x=0}, \\
&\dots
\end{aligned}$$

To calculate the rotational stiffnesses the moments of the reaction forces about the coordinate system axes are required. The moment around the x-axis caused by reaction force F_1 is:

$$M_{1,Rx-x} = [1 \ 0 \ 0]^T \cdot (\vec{F}_1 \times \vec{b}_1)$$

The total moments around the three axes are:

$$M_{Rx-x} = [1 \ 0 \ 0]^T \cdot \sum_{n=1}^9 \vec{F}_n \times \vec{b}_n,$$

$$M_{Ry-x} = [0 \ 1 \ 0]^T \cdot \sum_{n=1}^9 \vec{F}_n \times \vec{b}_n,$$

...

The linearized elements of the stiffness matrix are:

$$k_{Rx-x} = - \left. \frac{\partial M_{Rx-x}}{\partial s_x} \right|_{s_x=0},$$

$$k_{Ry-x} = - \left. \frac{\partial M_{Ry-x}}{\partial s_x} \right|_{s_x=0},$$

...

Repeating this for all other directions results in equation 2, the complete stiffness matrix of the suspension.

- For a two stage suspension, both suspensions act in series, in a moving base – spring – mass – spring – mass configuration:

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_1 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & M_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{s}_1 \\ \ddot{s}_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_1 + K_2 & -K_2 \\ -K_2 & K_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \end{bmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} M_1 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & M_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \ddot{u}_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The centers of gravity and suspension points (the b's) are in the same plane. Subscript 1 refers to the inner suspension and subscript 2 to the outer suspension.

Section 3. Thermal model

- The core temperature will not be significantly higher than the outer temperature of the cords. From equation 14 the largest P_{cord} is expected to be 1.0 W for the highest random vibration levels. The measured temperature at those levels is 171°C and the (axial) conductivity is 4.45 W/Km according to the formula in table 1 for this temperature. Then equation 10 gives a ΔT of 0.9 °C if $\lambda_{tr} = \lambda$ and 9.0 °C if $\lambda_{tr} = 0.1\lambda$.
- For $h = 84 \text{ W/Km}^2$, $r = 0.000442808 \text{ m}$ and $\lambda = 0.1 \cdot 4.45 \text{ W/Km}$, the Biot number is 0.04.
- The specific heat of Kevlar depends on temperature according to the manufacturer's data. The formula in table 1 is a linear interpolation in the temperature range of interest for this article. To determine the heat capacity of a cord the maximum recorded temperature of it can be used. The temperatures in the cord ends will be somewhat lower, but on the other hand the temperatures towards the core of the cord will be a bit higher.
- The power that is dissipated in the four cords undergoing the highest loads is less than 100% of the power input. It is about ~70% according to data analysis. The rest is dissipated in other parts of the test model, including the other 5 cords. A new test model will be made wherein the metallic parts are replaced by a monolithic structure, to limit the amount of energy dissipation in the non-Kevlar parts of the structure.

Section 5.1 – Temperature recordings

- Figure 10:

The shaker needs ~1.0 sec to fully develop the random load, this was taken into account when fitting to an exponential function.

- The difference between the time constants for when the shaker started and when it stopped can be explained by the nature of the convection. When the shaker is active, the convection is forced. When the shaker is turned off, the convection is natural. Therefore two different conductive heat transfer coefficients are expected, with a higher conductive heat transfer coefficient for forced vibration and thus a lower time constant.

Section 5.2 – Sinusoidal vibration tests

- Necessary checks to confirm the accelerometers were placed in the right directions and correlation checks were performed.
- Degradation of the central cord in the 7 strand setups, see figure 19, could be an explanation why the first eigenfrequency for the 7 strand setups is somewhat lower than expected.
- Equation 15:

For an exponential sweep:

$$\eta = \frac{Q^2 R \ln(2)}{60 f_k}$$

With:

$$Q^2 = \left(\frac{1}{2\zeta}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{4\zeta^2}$$

The equation becomes:

$$\eta = \frac{R \ln(2)}{240 \zeta^2 f_k}$$

- Figure 11:

In such a system bifurcations occur if the nonlinearity is strong enough; the jump would occur at a different frequency depending on if the sweep is up or down, in between are 3 solutions, 2 stable ones and an unstable solution. No evidence was found for this in the frequency response tests. The measured peak frequencies in the resonance search tests were the same for the up and down sweep but the sweep rate was too fast to capture the steady state response of the system due to its temperature dependency.

By repeating this test at different amplitudes and constructing the backbone curve of the response peak the true unperturbed eigenfrequency can be found. This was not done because it was too time consuming and it is expected that these frequencies will not be that much different than those in table 1.

- Possible slacking during the frequency response tests:

The deformations of the cords were not measured directly but can be derived from the accelerometer data. The absolute accelerations of the mass and the base were measured. The amplitude of the sinusoidal motion of the mass is much larger than the amplitude of the sinusoidal motion of the base. The phase lag between the two was also measured, it is -90 degrees. In this case, the amplitude of the absolute acceleration of the mass can be used as if it were the amplitude of the relative acceleration between the mass and the base.

For the frequency response of 2B, the largest amplitude of the frequency response (output/input) was 60.71, at 569.3 Hz. With an input of 1.2 g the amplitude of the mass is 72.852 g. This is $72.852 \text{ g} \cdot 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2/\text{g} = 714.67812 \text{ m/s}^2$. The amplitude of the displacement is $\omega^{-2} = (2\pi f)^{-2}$ times the amplitude of the acceleration. That results in a 0.055856 mm displacement.

Cord 1,3,7 & 9 deform the most under loads in the y-direction. The vector of cord 3 is:

$$b_3 - a_3 = 20 \text{ mm} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix}$$

The new length is cord 3 plus the displacement:

$$\left| 20 \text{ mm} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0.0558556 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ mm} \right| = 20.042 \text{ mm}$$

The strain is: $20.042 \text{ mm}/20 \text{ mm} - 1 = 0.2096\%$. The change in force by this strain is $\Delta F = kL\epsilon = 334.57 \text{ N}$. For the frequency response of 2A this was less.

The X and Z accelerations were not recorded in this specific test. To see what the influence of them would be a worst-case scenario is used. Assume that the X and Z accelerations are half as large as the Y accelerations and they are phased such that the X, Y and Z motions constructively increase the length of the cord.

The largest cord length will be: $\left| 20 \text{ mm} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0.028 \\ 0.056 \\ 0.028 \end{pmatrix} \text{ mm} \right| = 20.068 \text{ mm}$. In that case the

strain is 0.3398% . The change in force by this strain is: 542.25 N . The change in force is less than the pretension of 550 N , yet the stiffness nonlinearity is obviously there. The nonlinear stiffness is not caused by slacking of the cords.

The loss in pretension does play a role in the loss of stiffness, in the F_0 terms of the stiffness matrix. These terms are small, and the resulting changes are negligible.

Section 5.3 – Random vibration tests

- Equation 17:

See equation 2.127 in Wijker - Random Vibrations in Spacecraft Structures Design. The term $\ddot{u}_{asd,y}$ can be considered a constant, with zero phase.

Section 5.3.1 – Measurement results

- The determination of the heat transfer coefficient is based on the time constants when the shaker was started, when the convection was forced.
- The linearized radiative heat transfer coefficient is $h_{rad} = 4\epsilon T_{avg}^3 \sigma_{SB}$ for a small object in a large surrounding. For a cord with the highest recorded temperature this results in $h_{rad} = 8.5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$. This is $8.5/84 = 10\%$ of the measured heat transfer coefficient. At room temperature this is less because $T_{avg} = T_{room}$, then $h_{rad} = 5.4 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$.
- Figure 13:
No sub- or superharmonics are visible in the figure.

Section 5.3.2 – Nonlinearities of the response

- If the damping were to be modelled with viscous damping, the damped eigenfrequencies would be slightly lower than the undamped eigenfrequencies. A simple check reveals that this is by far not enough to explain the measured drop in eigenfrequencies. If the damping were modelled with loss factor damping there would be no difference between the damped and undamped eigenfrequency, same for coulomb friction. The damping is more complicated than these simple models suggest.
- Equation 18:
This is the instantaneous stiffness, not the equivalent linear stiffness that can be derived with statistical linearization for random vibration.
- Calculation of the strain and strain rates for the random vibration tests:

The strain and strain rates were not measured directly but conservative estimates can be made based upon measurement data. There are 2 methods how these can be estimated.

Assume the base is standing still (1).

Use Mile's equation or for a 1 DOF systems with the frequency and damping of the first mode (2).

1 - Base standing still:

If the base is assumed to be standing still the motion of the mass can be used as if it were the relative motion between the mass and the base. This will lead to an overestimation of the actual strains and strain rates but that is OK, since we are interested in worst case values. As before, assume that the measured accelerations constructively combine into an elongation of cord 3.

The ASD of the mass was recorded in $[g^2/Hz]$ for frequencies between $f_1 = 100$ Hz and $f_2 = 1200$ Hz. To convert this to $[(m/s^2)^2 / Hz]$ multiply these values by $(9.81 [m/s^2 / g])^2$. Then, for the VSD (velocity spectral density) multiply each value by $1/\omega^2$. The rms velocity is:

$$\sqrt{\int_{f_1}^{f_2} VSD(f) df}$$

The values for the displacement spectral density (DSD) are the values for the VSD times $1/\omega^2$. The rms displacement is:

$$\sqrt{\int_{f_1}^{f_2} DSD(f) df}$$

This was done in the excel file that is in the data package.

The method described above is now applied to the random vibration test 2B.

The rms displacement in x-direction was: 1.64294E-5 m.

The rms displacement in y-direction was: 1.12138E-4 m.

The rms displacement in z-direction was: 1.77991E-5 m.

This shows that the accelerations are not just in the y-direction. Cross talk like this is to be expected in real world systems. The largest strains and strain rates appear in cord 1, 3, 7 & 9 equally. The worst case displacement (rms) for cord 3 is:

$$\text{The new cord length will be (3 sigma): } \left| 20 \text{ mm} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix} + 3 \begin{pmatrix} 0.0164294 \\ 0.112138 \\ 0.0177991 \end{pmatrix} \text{ mm} \right| = 20.301 \text{ mm}$$

The strain is (3 sigma): $100\% \cdot (20.301 \text{ mm} / 20 \text{ mm} - 1) = 1.5052 \%$. The 3-sigma values are used as maximum worst case values in the engineering of spacecraft structures. In a shaker test, the random load inputs are limited to 3-sigma values.

The rms velocity in x-direction was: 0.057772419 m/s.

The rms velocity in y-direction was: 0.257972306 m/s.

The rms velocity in z-direction was: 0.086186954 m/s.

The worst case velocity (3 sigma) for cord 3 is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0.1733 \\ 0.7739 \\ 0.2586 \end{pmatrix} \text{ m/s}$$

The velocity in the direction of the cord is the projection of the velocity vector onto the normalized cord vector:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0.1733 \\ 0.7739 \\ 0.2586 \end{pmatrix} \text{ m/s} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix} / \left| \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix} \right| = 0.7848 \text{ m/s (3 sigma)}$$

The strain rate is: $0.7848 \text{ (m/s)} / 0.020 \text{ m} = 39.238 \text{ /s (3 sigma)}$

2 - Check with the response of an equivalent 1 DOF system.

For a 1 mass-spring-damper system the response in terms of the relative motion is [equation 11.63 in Wjker- Mechanical vibrations in spacecraft design]:

$$w_{y,rms} = \sqrt{\frac{\ddot{u}_{y,ASD}}{8\zeta(2\pi f_n)^3}}, \quad \dot{w}_{y,rms} = \sqrt{\frac{\ddot{u}_{y,ASD}}{8\zeta(2\pi f_n)}}$$

For 2B:

$$f_n = 531 \text{ Hz}$$

$$\zeta = 0.023$$

The input ASD was 18 g (19 g is not considered because the suspension failed at that level). $18 \text{ g} \cdot 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 / \text{g} = 180.77 \text{ m/s}^2$

$$\ddot{u}_{y,ASD} = 29.7 \text{ [m/s}^2\text{]}^2 / \text{Hz}$$

Thus:

$$w_{y,rms} = 0.065934 \text{ mm (rms)}$$

$$\dot{w}_{y,rms} = 0.2200 \text{ m/s (rms)}$$

The responses in X and Z have more jagged shapes instead of single peaks, these are unfit to be described by the response of a 1 DOF system.

$$\text{The 3 sigma displacement is: } \vec{w}_{rms} = 3 \begin{pmatrix} w_{x,rms} \\ w_{y,rms} \\ w_{z,rms} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0.19780 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ mm.}$$

$$\text{The new cord length will be (3 sigma): } \left| 20 \text{ mm} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0.19780 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \right| = 20.179 \text{ mm.}$$

The strain is (3 sigma): $100\% \cdot (20.149 \text{ mm} / 20 \text{ mm} - 1) = 0.7439 \%$.

The 3 sigma velocity is: 0.6599 m/s. The velocity in the direction of the cord is the projection onto the normalized cord vector:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0.6599 \text{ m/s} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix} / \left| \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{3}/4 \\ 3/4 \\ 1/2 \end{pmatrix} \right| = 0.4950 \text{ m/s (3 sigma)}$$

The strain rate is: $0.4950 \text{ (m/s)} / 0.020 \text{ m} = 24.748 \text{ /s (3 sigma)}$

The strain and strain rate are less than the ones found with the previous method, the discrepancy is because less of the response is included in this estimation.

Conclusions:

Assuming the base stands still gives a maximum of 1.5% strain and a strain rate of 39.2 /s. The 1DOF equation estimates the strain and strain rates to be less than that but both are in the same order of magnitude.

- Possible slacking of the cords during random vibration:

The estimated strains at the highest levels are high enough to cause slacking of the cords (see the previous note). With a strain of 1.5%, the force in the highest loaded cord is:

$$F = k\Delta L = kL\epsilon = 7.22\text{E}6 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}} \cdot 20\text{mm} \cdot 0.015 = 2166 \text{ N}$$

This is the 3-sigma force, it occurs only 0.3% of the time.

- The maximum temperatures in the cord were used to find the relationship between temperature and stiffness. The temperature at the ends is somewhat lower, but the core temperatures are a bit higher. If the cord is modelled as small spring elements in series, the total stiffness is dominated by the weakest elements, meaning the ones with the highest temperatures. So using the highest recorded temperatures will give a good approximation.

Section 5.3.3 – Suspension failure

- It is not known if slacking plays any role in failure of the suspension.

Section 6 – Conclusions

- More recent X-IFU instrument studies have shown that the expected launch loads exceed the strength of the Kevlar cords tested in this work. The design is updated with a thicker Kevlar cord and modified end-fittings. Several tests are performed on these new cord assemblies, such as determination of the total thermal expansion when the cords are cooled to below 10 Kelvin, see <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cryogenics.2023.103742>.